

Artch.id Competitive Strategy Analysis Based on the Theory of Five Generic Competitive Strategies

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

The development of technology is one of the main causes that changes people's consumption pattern in buying a product, for it offers more convenience in the transaction process. That ease ultimately creates a trend known as e-commerce and has a significant impact on various industrial sectors, including fashion. The fashion industry has the second largest growth rate after culinary. A large number of business actors that take part within the fashion industry has made the market competition even tighter, especially in Bandung. One of the industry's actors, who specifically focuses on bags, is Artch.id. In which Artch.id applies a strategy in order to continuously adjust on market demand. This research is a descriptive qualitative analysis, with the use of case study research methods. The focus of this research is aimed to review the implementation of Artch.id's strategy, whether or not it refers to the five generic competitive strategies theory in meeting consumer's demand and competing with its competitors by designing more specific programs. In analysing the data obtained, the author matches these data to the six dimensions that must be met based on the Five Generic Competitive Strategies. Based on the research results, it can be concluded that Artch.id has fulfilled the requirements in implementing the Best-Cost Provider Strategy dimension. Artch.id should evaluate the strategy and ensure that those dimensions can be maintained and developed so that service orientation to the consumers can be maximized

Keywords: STRATEGY, FIVE GENERIC COMPETITIVE STRATEGY

Introduction

According to (Seddon & Lewis, 2003), Porter argues that business strategy involves defining company's long-term position in the marketplace, making difficult trade-offs about what the company will and will not do to provide value to customers, and forging difficult-to-replicate fit among parts of the "activity system" the firm constructs to deliver value to customers, all with a goal of achieving a higher return on investment. Fashion as one of the sub-sectors of the creative economy, is the second-largest sub-sector after culinary, according to the (Central Statistic Agency, 2020). Fashion has had tremendous growth, with a 15,01% growth percentage, indicating that it is an excellent time to start a business in the fashion industry. Furthermore, with population of

2.497.938 people, Bandung's fashion market share is considered quite large (Central Statistic Agency of Bandung City, 2019). Moreover, with a total of 333.112 SMEs that vary in kinds, Bandung City is the third largest SMEs distribution level. This makes industrial competitiveness in the city of Bandung extremely tight, with all industrial sectors, including the bag industry, bearing the brunt of the consequences as well.

From many businesses in the fashion industry, Artch.id is one of the businesses with the main product are bags. Artch.id is in Southern Bandung, and has started operating since 2014. The name Artch.id is taken from the word "art", while "ch" is taken from the word change. It means the basis of Artch.id in carrying out its activities is to create products with high artistic value and at the same time continuously make innovative updates to each of its product with the intention of changing the mindset of people who view bags as only about models and designs. As bags have many added values and benefits that are able to give significant impact to customer through the form of collaboration in its design, usability, and supporting features. This company also has strong product characteristics in the form of product variation. In addition, the majority of the Artch.id's bags are made from high-quality waterproof polyester. Artch.id utilizes various online platforms for their business activity namely website and social media in order to reach a wider market so that they can compete with another competitor.

Based on the description above, the author is very interested in studying more deeply about the types of strategies that Artch.id has implemented in maintaining its existence to date and identifying it based on the approach of the Five Generic Competitive Strategies Theory. The title that the author has set in the preparation of this scientific paper is "Artch.id Competitive Strategy Based on Five Generic Competitive Strategies Theory".

Literature Review Strategy

Strategy is a basic series of actions that are implemented by all levels of an organization to achieve the goals of the organization (Siagian, 2004). Associated with the context of business activities, this is in line with the understanding according (Wright, Kroll, & Parnell, 1996), which states that the strategy is used as a facility used by management in achieving consistent performance that is in line with the mission and goals of the organization. Meanwhile, according to Mintzberg in a quoted by (Anderson & Artkins, 2001), strategy is a unit consisting of several elements in the organization including the main goals of the organization, policies, as well as the priority sequence of activities. These things are formulated into a concept of 5P Strategy. Each of these "P" elements has functions and roles that support the organization in the process of achieving its goals including:

- i) Strategy as a Plan, this phase formulates strategies based on brainstorming and in-depth research;
- ii) Strategy as a Ploy, talking about the process/method of implementing the plan;
- iii) Strategy as a Pattern, as harmonization between strategic planning and its implementation;
- iv) Strategy as a Position, an alternative way for the organization to position itself in the current market situation;
- v) Strategy as a Perspective, talking about the

culture that influences and is embraced by the organization so as to create a new perspective on the work culture and goal achievement. (Nickols, 2016), classify there are at least three level of strategies are widely accepted, including: i) Enterprise level strategy; ii) Business unit level strategy and; iii) Functional level strategy.

Strategic Management

According to (Mullins & Walker, 2013), a well developed strategy contains five components or sets of issues 1) The Scope of an organization refers to the breadth of its strategic domain the number and types of industries, product lines, and market segments it competes in or plans to enter; 2) Goals and Objectives such as volume growth, profit contribution, or return on investment over specified time periods for each of those businesses and product markets and for the organization as a whole; 3) Resource Deployment, formulating a strategy also involves deciding how those resources are to be obtained and allocated, across business, Product markets, functional departments, and activities within each business or product market; 4) Identification of a Sustainable Competitive Advantage. specification of how the organization will compete in each business and product market within its domain; 5) Synergy, enables the total performance of the related businesses to be greater than it would otherwise be: The whole becomes greater than the sum of its parts.

(Siagian, 2004) explains that strategic management is a series of fundamental decisions and action made by top management and implemented to by all levels within an organization to achieve organizational goals. (David, 2015) also defines strategic management as the science of the formulation, implementation of the formulation, and evaluation of the implementation of function that enable an organization to achieve its goals. Strategic management consists of several important stages, , namely as follows: i) Formulating Strategy, determining the vision and mission, identifying opportunities and threats from internal and external perspectives and designing long-term goals that are packaged into a strategy that is considered the most relevant; ii) Implementing Strategy, This stage is better known as the “action stage” with the aim of translating the strategy formulation so that it can be realized by the organization; iii) Evaluating Strategy, the organization has the authority and responsibility to be able to measure whether the implementation has been going well in accordance with the organization's goals, or are there still various obstacles.

The Five Generic Competitive Strategies

This theory is the result of a modification of the classic generic strategy which is more in analysing 5 competitive advantages. (Doyran, 2020) state that there are three strategic approaches that have the potential to be superior to competitors in the business industry, including: 1) Low-cost Leadership, 2) Differentiation, 3) Focus. Along with the development of the business climate, (Campbell-Hunt, 2000) stated that the generic strategy previously proposed by Porter has been modified into the Five Generic Competitive Strategies approach including:

- **Low-cost Provider**

The company's approach for attracting a larger and wider target market by giving low product pricing to gain

consumer interest. There are two areas that the company can implement to grasp this method. To begin, set prices that are low in comparison to competitors' prices in order to attract price-sensitive buyers and grow sales. Second, with a reshuffle of the supply chain in industrial operations, manage the present price. As a result, the focus of this strategy approach is on establishing cheaper prices as a competitive advantage (Thompson, Peteraf, & Gamble, 2015).

- **Broad Differentiation**

A strategy in which the company offers products that are different from those offered by competitors to a large target market. In this context, the products offered to consumers are unique (not easily imitated by competitors), and the final goal is said to be achieved when the company is able to set special prices for products with limited quantities that can still be accepted and purchased by consumers, as well as create consumer loyalty to brands from related companies (Thompson, Peteraf, & Gamble, 2015).

- **Best-cost Provider**

A strategy that, when implemented, gives additional value to customers based on a mix of high-quality product and competitive pricing compared to competitors. Unlike Low-Cost Providers, this strategy is more focused on the demands of customers in a smaller market niche, with the goal of predicting competitors' strategies. The success of this strategy approach hinges on the company's ability to pique the interest of consumers who are concerned not only about pricing, but also about the product's additional value (Thompson, Peteraf, & Gamble, 2015).

- **Focused Low-cost Provider**

This strategy is more focused on certain market sectors, and it does not compete with other competitors that are aiming for a specific market share at a lower cost. In general, this strategy is more focused on consumer demands in the specialized market sectors company (Thompson, Peteraf, & Gamble, 2015).

- **Focused Differentiation**

The implementation of this strategy concentrated on a narrowed market segment and offers superior products that have been designed to appeal to the unique needs of specific consumer groups where this has previously been identified and designed carefully. These strategy success parameters depend on the existence of groups of consumers with special product needs and are based on the company's ability to compete with other competitors with similar target markets

The research method includes procedures and techniques used by researchers in identifying various problems (Sugiyono, 2013). In other words, the research method is defined as a scientific way to obtain data from Artch.id whose validity has been tested with goals that can be determined, developed, and proven, so the company can obtain knowledge that is used to understand, solve, and overcome the problems faced by Artch.id.

Data Collection Technique

This study applies two data collection techniques that are needed through: 1) Interview, used not only to obtain general information but also aims to find out more in-depth information for obtaining more accurate and factual

information. 2) Document study, facilitating to collect data and information from books, archives, documents, written numbers, and pictures from reports and pre-existing information to support the credibility of the research. This method is considered important because it supports the analysis from the point of view of previous studies.

Data Sources

Primary data is data that has never existed or compiled by any party. This data refers to information directly obtained by the author as a researcher from Artch.id according to the actual conditions that occurred. Secondary data is data that has been presented by other parties. This study uses it as a reference for information in the preparation process in the form of statistical data, private or government publications, official website, company data as primary data validation, etc.

Data Analysis Techniques

The analytical technique applied by the role is to be able to identify the fulfilment of the dimensions of the modification strategy that has been carried out by Artch.id. This theoretical dimension talks about the important things that Artch.id must have to be able to maintain business existence, product advantages, and compete in this business industry. The final goal of the analysis is applied to assess whether Artch.id has already met the various dimensions required in accordance with the theory in its business activities.

Research Model

Analysis

The company was founded in 2010 with the company name was “architect” and then re-branded in 2014 by changing its name to Artch.id. Based on the results of the interview, it can be seen that the present strategy implemented by Artch.id has fulfilled several dimensional requirements of the best-cost provider strategy

approach including, 1) strategic target; 2) basis of competitive advantage; 3) product lines; 4) production emphasis; 5) marketing emphasis and; 6) keys to sustaining the strategy. In addition, this company also pays full attention to its market share to always meet the demands of various consumers based on their characteristics and consumption patterns. The implementation of this strategy is proven by the comparison of the product variants offered between Artch.id and competitors in the same industry, which is as follows:

ARTCH.ID	NIION	EUCKFORLIFE
Backpack	Backpack	Backpack
Camera Bags	Clutch Bags	Packable Bags
Hand Bags	Laptop Bags	Sling Bags
Laptop Bags	Sport Bags	String Bags
Sack Bags	Sling Bags	Tote Bags
Sling Bags		Waist Bags
Tote Bags		
Travel Bags		
Waist Bags		

Artch.id began to direct the focus on developing product advantages and uniqueness as a basis for meeting consumer demand while competing with its business competitors. Seeing the reach of the target market for millennials with characters that tend to get bored easily, Artch.id consistently strives to continue to procure products for various consumers and update product attributes to anticipate this. In addition, the company is also at the stage of implementing a strategy to further highlight the product's identity in the eyes of consumers through an emphasis on the functional aspects of the product.

Five Generic Competitive Strategy

Through a generic competitive strategy, Artch.id doesn't seem to be realized that the company has fulfilled and even developed several dimensions of the best-cost provider. In its application, this strategy provides added value to consumers based on a combination of product attributes that are considered high-quality with competitive pricing compared to competitors. This strategy is aimed at the needs of buyers in the market segment which is more oriented to the added value of the product beyond price and design also can be a solution for Artch.id to overcome the similarities in the implementation of conventional strategies by its competitors. Based on the results of the interview, Artch.id has realized five of them. One dimension that is sufficient to represent the reason why this company is implementing a best-cost provider strategy approach is the feature updates that are continuously carried out by Artch.id. Furthermore, the author will show the correlation of the fulfilment of these dimensions to the activities that have been carried out by Artch.id to date, including:

Strategic Target

Artch.id targeting millennials as their market with an age range of 24-35 years old. But in fact, most of the target age groups who consume their products range from 17-25 years old.

- First, the target of the product offered is cross-segmented.
- The second is regarding the adjustment of demand for many consumers, which is applied by Artch.id in almost all types of products as a form of consistency in order to meet market demand.

Almost all types of products represent several groups of consumers targeted by this company such as Travel Bags KINGX which targets travelers, Sling and Waist Bags which target young people who "like to hang out", and so are several other types of products. Because it is too focused on adjusting market demand, Artch.id seems to have forgotten to prioritize specific targets so that the orientation of the services offered has not run optimally, however, this does not mean that this company has not missed the attention. Artch.id is deemed to have not fulfilled this dimension because it is still too focused on adjusting demand in various circles in the market. Therefore, it is very important for Artch.id to determine a specific target market so that this strategy can be implemented effectively.

Basis of Competitive Advantage

This dimension shows the company's ability to provide superiority to a product. Evidence of competitive advantage that is owned by Artch.id is based on several things including:

- Product branding that has been recognized, especially in the West Java region
- Quality of operational activities as evidence that production quality is a major concern in the form of the existence of various production machines that are in well-maintained condition to print products in bulk in accordance with quality standards
- Manpower organized through divisions and their job descriptions are adjusted to the good quality of workers
- Business activity control management applied by top management from Artch.id itself to ensure that every activity carried out is directly proportional to the process of achieving company goals

Product Line

Artch.id can present attractive products, including by updating solutions that are based on market research and consumer behavior patterns. Although based on the millennial characteristics (the tendency to get bored easily), Artch.id can overcome this problem because it has a qualified competitive advantage. Artch.id's production activities are supported by the company's operational functions whose qualifications are guaranteed. Until now, the entire production process implemented by Artch.id is mostly carried out by its employees. This company is also in producing bag products from the beginning it already has its own vendor but does not rule out the possibility to cooperate with other vendors in the context of procuring quality products. As a form of control over its business operational functions, Artch.id also routinely checks the condition and suitability of the production quantity (anticipating over production).

Production Emphasis

This dimension has been presented by Artch.id through the concept of "series" of several superior products where the latest series of the product in question, beside undergoing design, model, or colour upgrade, they will also continue to apply updates to product features and attributes. For example, the types of products "Tasche" and "Ovytaska" are products with the concept of "series" with the highest level of sales in recent years.

In addition to the current product design, this product is considered to always have a strong appeal so that until now there are still many consumers who buy this product. Starting from the 1.0 series which is made of canvas, the 2.0 series which starts to use polyester as a base material, also the 3.0 series which offers a new design made of waterproof material, to the 4.0 series design which based on the results of an interview with the owner of Artch.id stated that in this latest series, the production of bags is not only limited to design or basic materials but will emphasize the functional side of the bag itself in the form of adding a USB slot feature and a slot for a headset whose average pricing is competitive with competitors.

Marketing Emphasis

Artch.id has marketing activities, the majority of which are online, starting from the marketing process, transactions, to product distribution. Specifically, regarding the marketing process, this company is very utilizing existing facilities and technology through various online platforms as a medium through several important pillars including:

- Content and Gimmick

An important indicator regarding of digital marketing of a product as an attraction is a way of how businesspeople communicate the value of their products to the market share in an attractive way. So far, Artch.id's implementation of content and gimmicks tends to utilize Instagram social media in the form of videos, feeds, and Instagram stories. Reporting from (Pertiwi, 2016), the daily active users of Instagram Stories crossed the 300 million mark and is predicted to continue to grow. Likewise with video content, it was reported that throughout 2017, 90% of the content presented on the internet was in the form of videos and is predicted to continue to increase in the following years. In fact, around 64% of consumers decide to buy a product after seeing the offer via video. Related to this data, Artch.id is equally good at using this indicator to compete for attention from market share. This can be proven through the number of followers of the official Instagram account Artch.id which has reached more than 31,000 users.

- Partnership

Artch.id realizes this marketing activity through two sides, namely digital and conventional approaches. For marketing with a digital approach, the company collaborates with 80 several marketplaces, influencers, utilizes social media platforms in the form of advertising services, as well as collaborates with several business units for content games and gimmicks. Furthermore, for marketing with a conventional approach, Artch.id tends to be more inclined to collaborate with business partners carrying the concept of re-seller or dropship with several fashion outlets or distributions which until now have spread to several cities in Indonesia (Such as Garut, Makasar, Jambi, and Bali).

- Advertisement

Artch.id makes good use of this indicator in reaching a wider target market. Based on the results of interviews, advertising services through online platforms is one of the most profitable means because it helps this company in reaching a previously unreachable target market. What's more, this indicator is also considered as one of the

strong reasons why Artch.id can experience cross-market segmentation which is profitable because it affects the increase in profit. Until now, Artch.id has tended to focus its product offerings through advertising services from social media, namely Facebook and Instagram Ads.

- Endorsement

If content and gimmicks are likened to a way to communicate the value of a product, then related to this indicator, influencers are individuals who act as actors in this value communication activity. In contrast to advertising, Artch.id feels that influencers can communicate product values more personally and creatively. Until now, Artch.id has implemented a partnership with two official brand ambassadors from influencers.

- Membership Program

In the form of attractive offers as a positive response of Artch.id to consumers who have purchased its products as well as to create and maintain customer loyalty. This membership program is aimed at consumers who must agree to special terms and conditions in the form of Standard Operational Standards (SOP) which then requires consumers to have a member card and then can get a discount of up to 20% for several transaction processes until the deadline period that has been set. set. This membership program also applies both online and offline.

Key to Sustaining the Strategy

Based on interviews, Artch.id's achievements so far cannot be separated from the role of a good financial function including:

- Product Pricing

Basically, the price application process is strongly influenced by external factors of a business through the existence of stakeholders (including consumers, suppliers, competitors, and so on). However, after conducting interviews with parties from Artch.id, external factors were not the main reason in the pricing process, but internal factors. Initially, the company determined that profits from business activities should be kept to a minimum, the nominal value of which was not much different from the percentage of COGS. However, after some time, several obstacles were found since Artch.id began to recognize and utilize paid advertising services from various platforms, namely the fund allocation system that began to be out of sync.

- Determination of Budget and Sales Target

This company has a budget and sales targets that must be in sync with one another. Regarding sales targets, Artch.id has never set a percentage increase in sales that must be achieved but instead applies a benchmark that sales every month must be higher than the previous month.

- Investor's Role

Artch.id also has investors with the concept of Sharia and Family. Investors in question are workers who invest time, energy, and responsibility for the process of achieving company goals. Therefore, the concept of Sharia and Family is considered the right choice for a conducive work environment

- Financial Recording System

Regarding the financial recording system, this company uses the same infrastructure as businesses in general,

namely financial records using Microsoft Excel. However, in stock selling activities, Artch.id has an application called “ERAS”.

This application is specially designed by means of a custom-made application which was previously officially purchased in full package by Artch.id where this special design was indeed implemented to suit the needs of this company for its business activities.

Conclusion

Based on the theory of Five Generic Competitive Strategies, Artch.id is assessed to apply a best-cost provider strategy approach which has previously been analyzed through the suitability of the six strategic dimensions (including strategic market; basis of competitive advantage; product line; production emphasis; marketing emphasis; and keys to sustaining the strategy). From these dimensions, Artch.id is considered to have met the requirements of these dimensions, so it can be concluded that Artch.id has so far been declared valid to apply the best-cost provide strategy approach. Artch.id also always strives to consistently match the needs of market share to the demand for a product. By choosing a market share in the millennial category, Artch.id of course already understands the characteristics of its market segment which tends to get bored easily and has doubts about its loyalty. Therefore, the implementation of the strategy implemented by Artch.id refers to the procurement of products in response to consumer demands in various circles of society.

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